

TUM DataTagger

A Tool for Efficient and Collaborative RDM

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Abstract

The TUM DataTagger is a user-friendly solution for efficient research data management (RDM) at the Technical University of Munich (TUM). It facilitates comprehensive documentation of research data through semi-automated metadata assignment and enables collaboration with project partners, both within and outside TUM.

From the outset, the needs of TUM researchers regarding RDM were assessed, and specific requirements for RDM solutions were identified. Based on these requirements, it was decided not to use an existing tool but to develop a new, openly available solution. The prototype of the new software was gradually tested in several usability studies by researchers from various TUM Schools and by TUM Data Stewards, and further optimized based on the feedback received.

The tool focuses on the following aspects:

- **Intuitive usability** through a clear user interface
- **Management of research data** during the research process in a simple structure
- **Minimal effort in documentation** using metadata through pre-fillable templates
- **Optional setup of team-specific guidelines** regarding folder structure and metadata vocabulary
- **Collaboration in research projects** by granting access rights to (external) project partners and giving permissions according to their specific roles
- **Unified interface** for accessing various secure storage solutions
- **Automatic versioning** upon file updating or metadata editing

The TUM DataTagger is an open-source software developed jointly by the TUM University Library and a software company. The presentation will introduce the user-oriented development process and explain how the mentioned focus aspects were addressed. It will also illuminate the control of the development and the integration of the project into the overall structure of the institution.

Keywords: RDM, Tool, Metadata, Collaboration

Resources

The material and resources (e.g. data, model, codes, documentation, videos) which underly, support or are closely related to your contribution deposited on a repository, please include a title, the respective DOI(s) and brief description. E.g.

- TUM DataTagger. <https://datatagger.ub.tum.de/> “Software that enables efficient and collaborative research data management.”
- Website. <https://www.ub.tum.de/en/datatagger> “Website that describes TUM Data-Tagger.”
- Repository. <https://github.com/TUM-DataTagger> “Website that will provide the code of TUM DataTagger soon.”

Author contributions

Sebastian Oeder contributed to software conceptualization, investigation, validation, and has written the original draft.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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